

Training and Development Practices in Public and Private Banks: A Comparative Study of Kenya and India

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Abstract

This paper was set to examine training and development in the banking sector and reaffirm the investment in training and development. In line with the assertion made by the literature and the evidences gathered in the process of the study, the following recommendations were made: It is an established fact that no serious minded organization like banks can be staffed by people with expertise and potentials in the various disciplines needed for its total functioning simply by recruitment and selection, it's the systematic training and development of personnel on continuous basis that can harness the totality of human resources in the organization, banks should ensure that any training and development which takes place is based on proper analysis of its contribution to the effectiveness and efficiency of banking industry. The data collected from different sources was cross checked. Different statistical tools and techniques were used like mean, mode, median, averages, t-test and chi-square. The paper concluded that investment in the area of training and development in the human resources will bear the fruits much fold for the banking industry of the two countries. For the Indian banks have established their training institutes for the purpose of training its staff which was lacking with their counterparts. Each employer who invests seriously in the area of Training and Development will reap the benefits of an enriched working environment with higher levels of staff retention as well as increased productivity and performance. In the modern computer era training has gained the reputation of dynamic concept which needs to be understood in that perspective most of the modern banks which do not respond to the dynamic change that are seen in changed environment may fail to respond to the needs of customers. Training is one of most important and effective means of bringing about change in banking sector. Hence, the study is carried with the aim of studying training implementation in these selected banks.

Key Words: Training and Development, Technology, efficiency, evaluation and performance.

Introduction

Human resource development does not serve the purpose of the organization along but the rationale for such a development is based on certain facts, truths and the value system based on the acceptance of the principle of human dignity. Every human being has a right to develop to whatever extent s/he can and in doing so, serves himself, the organization he works in, his

family and the society to the maximum possible extent and in the best possible manner.

Within banks, a major responsibility of the top management is to develop personnel through training and development. Training in this context, can be thought of as bank process of assisting employees in

enhancing their efficiency and effectiveness at work and cultivating appropriate behavior and attitudes towards work and customers. Training could be designed either for improving present capacities at work or for enabling him to assume higher responsibilities in future, which would call for additional knowledge, superior skills and changed attitudes. Every employee regardless of previous training, education and experience, need to be introduced to the work environment of new employers and to be taught to perform specific tasks.

Training is valuable to the employee in terms of better job security and greater opportunity for advancement. A skill thus acquired by the employee through training is an asset to the organization. Employee training represents a significant expenditure for most organizations. Training too often is viewed tactically rather than strategically. Bank managers are often not clear about what they want from training and therefore fail to connect training with the overall bank goals and strategy.

According to Ronald (1999) Training should not be regarded as a luxury to be undertaken when time and budgets allow. Nor is it wise to think of training as remedial, as a matter of shoring up weak employees or fixing problems. In a successful program, the training unit acts not like a group of physicians who minister to organizational ills, but rather as an agent of change. Senior management should recognize that the training function has valuable intelligence about employees' core skills. The training unit, in a successful program, understands the organizations strategic direction and can design and

implement a creative way of moving people in that direction. Many organizations including banks have already shifted their thinking about training function. They have seen for themselves that training is where skills are developed, attitudes are changed, ideas evolve and the organization is reinvented. In the course of learning the skills that will increase sales, build effective teams, improve quality, standards or meet a wide range of other objectives, employees create a new organizational culture.

As a result, banks have to continue to deal with two urgent challenges. The first is to improve their competitive position by reducing costs and the second is to learn how to manage the impact of technological development. This reality according to Coffman L (1990)²; has magnified the importance of successful training and development programs with measurable results.

Consequently training and development has become one of the most critical aspects of human resource management effectiveness. No matter the way one looks at training and development, they help employees to learn how to use the resources in an approved fashion that allows the organization to reach its desired output. Able people may grow to a point where they are ready for responsibilities beyond their initial assignment. When this happens, training and development become imperative. Training and development has grown concerned not only with helping individuals to adequately fill their positions, but also with helping whole organizations and sub departments grow and develop. Training and development, though primarily concerned with people, is

also concerned with technology, the precise way an organization does business. That technology might be the way a flight attendant greets a passenger on an air line, or the way an egg is fried, it might be the recipe that makes one soft drink, distinctly different from all other soft drinks. It might be the design that makes one automobile more attractive or more efficient than its competitors. It might include the procedures for mixing and bottling the drink, or for assembling the automobile. Training is concerned with the meeting between two inputs to organizational effectiveness, that is, people and technology. Since an organization can rarely secure people who are at the time of employment, total masters of their unique requirements, organizations need a good training and development programme. Training changes uninformed employees to informed employee; training changes unskilled or semiskilled workers. Every organization needs to have well trained and experienced people to perform the activities that have to be done. It is necessary to raise the skill levels and increase the versatility and adaptability of employees. Inadequate job redesigning or technological breaks through require some type of training and development efforts. In a rapidly changing organizational climate, employee training and development is not only an activity that is desirable, but also an activity that an organization must commit resources to, if it is to maintain a viable and knowledgeable workforce (Mamoria, 1996).

Review of Some Selected Literature

There is a wealth of information available concerned with the subject area of training

and development. Within the broader area, academicians and practitioners have devoted considerable thought to the various aspects related to planning, conducting and evaluating activities pertaining to training. The survey of related literature becomes essential to understand the previous research work carried out by various researchers in the field of training and development in general and in particular to banks. Aswathappa (2008) opines that training and development may be understood as imparting of specific skills, abilities and knowledge to an employee. More clearly, training and development may be understood as an attempt to improve current or future employee's ability to performance through learning, usually by changing the employees' attitude or increasing his or her skills and knowledge. Thus it is clear that from the above discussion many scholars argue that training is an act of increasing knowledge, skills, attitudes of an employees and improving the overall performance of the organization, however, at present most of the public and private organization not much focusing on training and development in view of this they are unable to get competitive advantages over competitors.

Wayne, (1998) in his study on "Examining the impact of training on business results through post training(ROI)" expressed that training expenses represent a substantial investment in training resources. The primary objective of the study was to determine if there were positive financial impacts of leadership training on business and present verifiable and valid, substantial

ROI with meaningfulness. The training was found to be both successful and effective in the teaching and developing strategic leadership concepts. Based on study's result, there was a meaningful difference Biswajeet, (2005) opine that "training is a systematic process of changing knowledge, skill, behavior and or motivation of employees to improve their performance on the job as per the goals and objectives of the organization". Of learning by the organization and that all participants have a net positive impact on business. It should facilitate introduction of new technology, new work methods, innovations and all round enhancement of productivity and quality of products and services. Training is an act of increasing knowledge, skill and attitude of an employee for improving his performance on the job.

Udai, and Rao (2006) in their article "Managing Innovations" expressed that training involves the use of formal processes to impart knowledge and help people to overcome traditional thinking and develop the ability of creative problem solving. People should be trained to look from a new perspective and be able to see opportunities outside. The training techniques used for improving innovations should be appropriate to job requirements, learning needs, previous experiences, and level of knowledge and skill of participants. Usually the techniques for enhancing creativity are brainstorming and systematic collection of fresh ideas. Programs of this nature can be applied to actual problems and the same time they provide ample opportunity for individuals to improve creativity thinking.

Organizations that want to be innovative must hire creative people and also train their HR people to access the creative potential of the candidates based on a set of criteria, after knowing the traits usually possessed by such people. Access to changing technology it's critical that executives realize the importance of training end users as their skills become obsolete. To this end, training end users in IT to perform their job is very important. End users who lack the appropriate knowledge to complete tasks effectively are in need of training. Reddy and Rathana (2007) argues that "the quality of an employee and their development to training and education are major factors in determining long term profitability of a small and big business. If you hire and keep good employee, it is wise to invest in developing their skills, to increase their productivity. Training is often considered for new employees only, which is a mistake, because ongoing training for senior employees helps them to update themselves of rapidly changing job requirements. His conclusion was that the overall training program was good and should be applicable to other Saudi companies. All trainees believe the training program provides a good opportunity to guide them to be knowledgeable and educative.

Blake (2006), in her study on "vertical transfers of training" expressed that the transfer training literature has focused primarily on individual as the unit of analysis. The question of whether training an individual influences a group's performance has yet to be investigated empirically. Her findings were that as the number of trained employees increased

beyond three the amount of influence exerted the fifth individual decreased. Extraversion moderated the relation between training an individual who was trained was an extrovert, vertical transfer increased. Collective efficacy mediated the relationship between training one or more individuals and groups performance.

Need for the Study

As the banks have in the past performed their functions fairly efficiently and effectively even without a very elaborate training effort; the question arises why does it become necessary to undertake a massive effort in the near future? The answer lies in the unprecedented quantitative and qualitative changes which have greatly increased the pressure on the personnel not only to continuously acquire new knowledge and skills but even to acquire traditional experience within a much shorter period of time Firstly, with the rapid expansion, promotions at all levels have been much faster. Whereas it used to take 25 years or more for a clerk to become an officer during the 1950s, it now takes approximately 5 years. Careful job rotation and formal training alone can prepare the clerical personnel to assume higher responsibilities within such a short time span. Secondly, new areas of responsibility, such as agricultural finance, small scale industry finance and export finance. This research study has been carried out analyze the problems and suggest measures to improve training and development in banks. Whereas the Indian banks have their own institutes which train its staff the Kenyan banks miss it out. The study aims to answer several research questions such as

analysis of training needs, training programmes, efficiency of training, approaches of trainees and attitudinal changes of employees after undergoing training, evaluation of training and its benefits and perception of employees towards evaluation of training.

Objectives of the Research Study

In the light of the above discussion relating to establishing the need of the research, the following are the objectives of the present research study:

1. To study the role of T & D in empowering employees to the success of the banking industry.
2. To examine the policies and practices of the banking sector regarding to their human resource development.
3. To study the various methods of T & D on how they are implemented to the banking industry.
4. To study the attitudes of bank employees towards the perception of T&D and to ascertain the effects of such training in relation to productivity.

In the light of the above objectives the following hypotheses have been formulated for research study.

Hypotheses for the Research Study

Two hypotheses have been designed for testing on the basis of the objectives of the present research study. These hypotheses are as under:

Hypotheses I: There is no relationship between the characteristics of employees of the banking sector regards to training in empowering employees.

Hypotheses II: There is no relationship between the two sectors relating to their policies in developing their human resources through training.

Research Design

The research design for the present research study is exploratory survey type. The setting for the research is in the field of banking industry in Kenya and India and data from the cross section of managers and employees has been collected for the analysis.

Sampling procedure

The sampling procedure followed in the present research study is that of simple random sampling, and the sample includes management and employees of both banking industry in both countries. The universe for the study is employees and managers of banks of the said countries, which are involved in planning, conducting and evaluating T & D programmes. Therefore, the study adopted simple random sampling method and selected 1260 respondents.

Sources of Data

Primary data is collected from the sample of both banks in the said countries by adopting simple random method through a well structured questionnaire. The secondary data has been collected from a number of sources like books, journals, bank annual reports, bulletins, published articles, news papers and dissertations. In addition to this the study also made use of online journals and websites.

Tools and techniques

The data collected from different sources was cross checked and coded in the code sheet. Later the coded data was entered into master code sheet after cross checking if any entry was missing. Different statistical tools and techniques were used like mean, mode, median, averages, t-test, z-test, f-test, chi-square and ANOVA.

Gender representation the banking sector

The researcher tried to establish the number of male and female employed in both public and private sector of banking industry. The following table indicates the results found out of the number of male and female employees.

Table 1 Gender of the Respondents

Gender profile of respondents					
Gender	India		Kenya		Total
	No:	%	No:	%	
Male	186	60.8	168	54.9	354(58.1)
Female	120	39.2	138	45.1	258(41.9)
Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)

Source: Field survey

The table clearly indicates that 60.8% of the employees of public bank were male whereas 39.2% were female in India. On the other hand 54.9% of the total employees

were male and 45.1% were female in Kenya. In all it can be concluded that in both countries male respondents were more 58.1% representing (354) in comparison to their counterparts female employees who were 41.9% representing (430) of the total human resource of the banking industry.

Table 2 Respondents age wise

Age	Country				Total
	India		Kenya		
	No. of respondents	%	No. of respondents	%	
20-30	28	9.2	38	12.4	66(10.7)
31-40	100	32.0	140	45.8	240(42.2)
41-50	140	45.8	120	39.2	260(39.0)
Above 51	40	13.0	8	2.6	48(7.8)
Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)

Source: field survey

As indicated from the table above majority of the bank employees is in the age group of 41-50 for both countries 45.8 % (140) and 39.2 % (120) respectively. Indian banks had the oldest employees above the age of 51 at 13%, whereas the Kenyan banks had the lowest at 2.6%. The private sector bank

regards young employees compared to public banks with 9.2% and 12.4% respectively. It can be concluded from the above table indicating that maximum respondents of all the two countries fall in the category of age group of 41-50.

Table 3 opinions of the respondents on the basis of level of education

Education wise profile of sample of respondents					
Education	India		Kenya		Total No:
	No:	%	No:	%	
High School	-	-	-	-	-
P.U.C/College	10	3.3	8	2.6	18(2.9)
Graduation	160	52.0	80	26.0	240(39.0)
Post graduation	98	31.8	170	55.2	268(43.5)
Others (specify)	40	13.0	50	16.2	90(14.6)
Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)

Source: field survey

From the table above showing the importance the banks give to the education level of its human resources. The Indian banks respondents has the lowest level of education attainment as compared to the Kenyan banks since most of the employees

are graduates, while a majority of the Kenyan respondents are post-graduates. Nearly one fourth of the total respondents are graduates while approximately 43.5 % is post- graduates and while 14.6% of the total number respondents have specialized

qualification in the area of Training & Development. It can be concluded from the above table that in all the two countries banks majority of the respondents 45% were graduates.

For the purpose of the study managers were asked to rate the most impending barriers relating to training received by respondent in between service period. The findings relating to trainings have been tabulated as below:

Table 4 opinions of Manager Respondents on barriers of training

Barriers of T&D						
Barriers	India		Kenya		Total No:	Total %
	No:	%	No:	%		
Funding	9	60	8	53	17	57
Time	6	40	7	47	13	43
Total	15	100	15	100	30	100

Source: field survey

Table 4 indicates the barriers to training and development as indicated by the managers of both countries. It was a question asked to the management to identify two of the main barriers to his/her individual success. Funding and time were identified as major barriers funding was cited by 17 respondents representing (57%) while time was indicated by 13 respondents representing (43%). This is no surprise – the

researcher anticipated this result after the extensive review of the literature. The funds allocated for training and development are not sufficient. Factors that obstruct learning within the banks were the subject of the next question. Every manager spoke of time and time-related issues as a major factor impeding training. This, too, was not a surprise. Banks are expected to do more with little budget to add needed positions.

Table 5 opinions of the Manager respondents on areas of most training need

Most Pressing Training Need for Manager Position as Identified by Managers						
Pressing Training need	India		Kenya		Total No:	Total %
	No:	%	No:	%		
Customer relationship management	6	40	4	27	10	33
Handling of complaints	3	20	3	20	6	20
Risk management	2	13	5	33	7	23
Leadership management	2	13	2	13	4	13
Performance management	2	14	1	7	3	11
Total	15	100	15	100	30	100

Sources: Field survey

It's clear from table above that managers were asked to give their opinions towards the most pressing need of training and customer relationship management was mentioned by 10 managers representing 33.33% as the most training pressing need for managerial training. Risk management

was also given 23.3% representing 7 of the respondents; Handling of complaints was the next of three needs most often mentioned. Leadership management training and Performance management were also cited by 20%, 13.3% and 10% respectively.

Table 6 Opinions of the respondents on Evaluation of T&D

Performance	Evaluation of T&D						
	India		Kenya		Total	Degree of Freedom	X ²
	No:	%	No:	%		5%	
Above average	176	57.1	108	35.1	284(46.1)		
Average	106	34.4	180	58.4	286(46.4)		
Poor	26	8.4	20	6.5	46(7.5)		
Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)		X ² =121.341

Source: field survey

The table above shows evaluation of training and development as being evaluated by the banks. Training and development of both countries has been average 46.4% (286) by total response. T&D is said to be above average and poor by 46.1% and 7.5% respectively. But when individual results are analyzed 57.1% of the Indian respondents equate T&D as above average whereas in Kenya its 35.1%. Further it can be deduced from the calculated x² that the calculated x² is 121.341 which greater than the table value of x², therefore null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is no difference as to the training and developments of the banks.

Research Finding Relating to Training and Development in both countries (Banks):-

For the purpose of research work various aspects were studied relating to training – like training received by the respondent in between service period or not, problem faced by respondents, number of training programmes attended, area in which they will like to attend training, satisfaction with training programmes, effectiveness of training programmes etc. the findings of training have been tabulated below:

Table 7 Opinions of the respondent’s on Training in between service period: Bank- wise breakup of respondents on the basis of whether they received training in between service period or not:

S.No	Response Category	Respondent Bank				Respondents
		India	%	Kenya	%	
1	Yes	200	65.0	210	68.2	410(66.6)
2	No	108	35.0	98	31.8	206(33.4)
	Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)

Source: Field survey

It clear from the table above that 66% of the total human resources of the banking industry acknowledged that there was training in between the service, and the

other human resources said no. When analyzed separately, it can be recognized that that 65% and 68.2% India and Kenya banks respondents acknowledged of having

training in between the services. Whereas, 35% and 31.8% respondents of both countries banks opined that they have never had training in between services.

To test the training being given by both banks of these countries whether there was any difference we carried out a chi-square

test. The calculate value of χ^2 is 2.1882 and the table value of χ^2 for degree of freedom at 5% level of significance is 5.991 since the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value it indicates that there is no significant difference among the two banking sectors on the basis of training received or not.

Table 8 Bank- wise breakup of respondents on the basis of training received

Response Category	Respondent Bank				Respondents	Chi-square df at 5%
	India	%	Kenya	%		
Theoretical Training	120	39.0	140	45.6	260(42.2)	
On -the-job Training	100	32.5	70	22.7	170(27.6)	
Off -the- job training	88	28.5	98	31.8	186(30.2)	
	308	100	308	100	616(100)	0.5834

Source: Field survey

From the table above showing the responses of the respondents on the basis of training received. 42.2% of the total respondents opined that they had received theoretical training, 30.2% of the respondents also acknowledged having received off -the- job training, while 27.6% also opined that they had received on -the-job Training. When each country bank is analyzed individually, 45.6% of the Kenya bank respondents as

compared to the 39% of the Indian acknowledged to have received theoretical training.

The calculate value of χ^2 is 0.5834 and the table value of χ^2 for 4degree of freedom at 5% level of significance is 9.488 since the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value it indicates that there is no significant difference among the two countries banking on the basis of training received.

Table 9 Bank- wise breakup of respondents on the basis of their training period

S.No	Response Category	Respondent Bank					Chi-square df at 6%
		India	%	Kenya	%	Total	
1	Few days	240	78.0	250	81.1	490(79.6)	
2	Few weeks	60	19.5	50	16.2	110(17.9)	
3	Six months	06	2.0	05	1.6	11(1.8)	
4	1-2 years	02	0.7	03	1.0	05(0.8)	
	Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)	3.99

Source: Field survey

It is vivid from the table above that the basis of training period that is accepted by most of the bank respondents is that training which lasts for few days as indicated by 79.6 percent of the total respondents. 17.9 percent opined the will prefer training period that lasts for few weeks. The Indian respondents when analyzed individually indicate that 78 percent preferred training period that lasted only for few days, where the respondents of Kenyan banks respondents 81.1 percent also preferred few days period of training. It can be concluded that majority of the respondents of both

banking sector acknowledged training that lasts for few days as being effective.

To test whether there was any difference between the training period undertaken by the two sectors, we carried a statically test using chi-square was carried out. The calculate value of χ^2 is 3.99 and the table value of χ^2 for 6 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance is 12.592 since the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value it indicates that there is no significant difference among the two banking sectors on the basis of training period of their employees.

Table 10 Bank- wise breakup of respondents on the basis of benefits training

S.No	Response Category	Respondent Bank					Chi-square df at 6%
		India	%	Kenya	%	Total	
1	Better	156	50.7	33	10.7	189(30.7)	
2	Job Satisfaction	102	33.1	125	40.6	227(36.9)	
3	Promotion	42	13.7	140	45.6	182(29.6)	
4	Not Helpful	08	2.6	10	3.3	18(2.9)	
	Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)	5.289

Source: Field survey

As indicated from the above table, 50.7 percent of the Indian respondents opined that they had benefited from the training given to by the bank and to them it was better, when the same question was posed to their counterparts in Kenya only 10.7 percent opined that the training was better. As regards to job satisfaction 33.1 of the Indian employees said they were satisfied, When the two countries are compared together, 36.9 percent of the total respondents opined that training has helped them in job satisfaction. 30.7 of the total respondents said training undertaken is better. 29.6 percent of the total respondents

where as 40.6 percent of their counterparts in the Kenyan opined to the same. The aspect that showed much difference is in the area of promotion were 45.6 percent of the Kenyan respondents said they are promoted as a result of training, whereas, 13.7 percent of their Indian respondents opined to the same.

were of the opinion that that training has helped them in scaling up in the promotions and only 2.9 percent were of the opinion that training has not helped them.

To analyze whether training has been beneficial to the employees we carried out a

chi-square test. The calculate value of χ^2 is 5.289 and the table value of χ^2 for 6 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance is 12.592 since the calculated value of χ^2 is less

than the table value it indicates that there is no significant difference among the two countries banking sectors on the basis of how training has beneficial the respondents.

Table 11 Bank- wise breakup of respondents on the basis of problems faced during training

S.No	Response Category	Respondent Bank					Chi-square df at 6%
		India	%	Kenya	%	Total	
1	Bias	20	6.5	30	9.7	50(8.1)	
2	Favoritism	80	26.0	148	48.0	228(37.0)	
3	Poor guidance	138	44.8	120	39.0	258(41.9)	
4	No problem	70	22.7	10	3.2	80(13.0)	
	Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)	8.933

Source: Field survey

From the table above showing problems faced by trainees during training period. It can be seen that 41.9 percent of the total respondents sighted that they have faced poor guidance from the superiors. 37 percent of the respondents have claimed to have experienced favoritism from the management during the training period. While, 13 percent and 8.1 percent have claimed to have faced no problem and bias respectively during the training time. But when analyzed independently 48 percent of the Kenyan respondents have faced Favoritism, whereas to the Indian sector

respondents only 26 percent opined to the same. 44.8 percent of the Indian respondents opined that they have received poor guidance during the training time, whereas the Kenyan respondents only 39 percent opined to the same.

The calculate value of χ^2 is 8.933 and the table value of χ^2 for 6 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance is 12.592 since the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value it indicates that there is no significant difference among the two banking sectors on the basis on the basis of problem faced by the respondents during training period.

Table 12 Bank- wise breakup of respondents on the basis of number of training programmes attended

S.No	Response Category	Respondent Bank					Chi-square df at 6%
		India	%	Kenya	%	Total	
1	1-2	7	2.3	28	9.1	35(5.7)	
2	3-4	30	9.7	160	52.0	190(30.8)	
3	5-6	170	55.2	120	39.0	290(47.1)	
4	More than 6	101	32.8	-	-	101(16.4)	

	Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)	2.367
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Source: Field survey

As shown in the table above indicating the number of training programmes attended by the trainees, it is clear that 57.1 percent of the total respondents have attended 5-6 training programmes. 30.8 of the total respondents have attended 3-4 training programme. While, 16.4 and 5.7 percent have attended training programmes for more than six times and 1-2 times respectively. When the two countries are compared separately the following are the results are vividly clear. 55.2 percent of the Indian sector banks respondents have attended training programmes 5-6 times, whereas, Kenyan sector bank respondents 39 percent opined to the same.

To find out whether any significant difference exists between the two sector

banks on the basis of number of training programmes attended by respondents in banks χ^2 was conducted. The calculate value of χ^2 is 2.367 and the table value of χ^2 for 6 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance is 12.592. Since the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value it indicates that there is no significant difference among the two banking sectors on the basis on the basis of problem faced by the respondents during training period.

Areas of training:-

Employees were asked to respond about areas in which they would like to take training to improve their effectiveness. The responses have been tabulated as follows:-

Table 13 Bank- wise breakup of respondents on the basis of areas they attend training

S.No	Response Category	Respondent Bank				
		India	%	Kenya	%	Total
1	General Mgt	116	37.7	98	31.8	214(34.7)
2	Marketing	72	23.4	100	32.5	172(28.0)
3	Personnel	50	16.2	56	18.2	106(17.2)
4	Finance	40	13.0	30	9.7	70(11.4)
5	Computer	30	9.7	24	7.8	54(8.8)
	Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)

Source: Field survey

As shown in the table above indicating the areas the trainees will like to attend training programmes on, it is clear that 34.7 percent of the total respondents would like general , finance and computer training areas respectively. When the two countries are compared separately the following are the results are vividly clear. 37.7percent of the Indian sector banks respondents would like general management as the area of training, whereas, the Kenya sector bank respondents 31.8 percent opined to the same. Marketing management is the other area whereby majority of Kenyan sector bank respondents would like to be trained in as represented by 32.5 percent, whereby Indian sector its 23.4 percent.

management area of training. On the hand 28 percent on marketing, 17.2, 11.4 and 8.8 on personnel

Table 14 Bank- wise breakup of respondents on the basis of their extent of satisfaction with training programmes

Response Category	Respondent Bank					Chi-square df at 6 %
	India	%	Kenya	%	Total	
To Great Extent	68	22.1	70	22.7	138(22.4)	
To Some Extent	105	34.1	125	40.6	230(37.3)	
To Little Extent	95	30.8	80	26.0	175(28.4)	
Not at All	40	13.0	33	10.7	73(11.9)	
Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)	1.872

Source: Field survey

The table above shows the extent of satisfaction with training programmes attended by trainees. It can be seen that 37.3 percent of the total respondents sighted that to some extent training has led to satisfaction in the work. 28.4 percent of the respondents opined too little extent they have had satisfaction in the work place. While, 22.4 opined that to a great extent they have had satisfaction in the work as a result of training programme they had attended. To the surprise of the researcher 11.9 of the total respondents opined not all have they been satisfied by the training in their work place.

To find out whether any significant difference exists between the two sectors banks on the basis of their extent of satisfaction with training programmes. The calculate value of x^2 is 1.872 and the table value of x^2 for 6 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance is 12.592. Since the calculated value of x^2 is less than the table value it indicates that there is no significant difference among the two banking sectors on the basis on the basis of satisfaction with training programme.

Table 15 Bank- wise breakup of respondents on the basis of effectiveness of training programmes:-

Response Category	Respondent Bank				
	India	%	Kenya	%	Total
Excellent	88	28.6	100	32.5	188(30.5)
Good	80	26.0	88	28.6	168(27.3)
Average	100	32.5	90	29.2	190(30.8)
Below Average	40	13.0	30	9.7	70(11.4)
Total	308	100	308	100	616(100)

Source: Field survey

From the table above showing the basis of effectiveness of training programmes it can be clearly seen that 30.8 percent of the total respondents of the banking sector rated the effectiveness of training programmes and

opined that it was above average. 30.5 percent opined that it was Excellent, 27.3 and 11.4 percent opined it was good and below average respectively.

Conclusions

Investment in the area of training and development in the human resources will

bear the fruits much fold for the banking industry of the two countries. Increasingly, high performing organizations like banks today are recognizing the need to use best training and development practices to enhance their competitive advantage. Training and development is an essential element of every banking business if the value and potential of its resources is to be harnessed and grown. The image of banking industry and of individual employers is also influenced by the extent and quality of staff training and development. Potential employees in such an open labour market will assess the track

Recommendations

This paper examined how banks carry on of training and development in the banking sector and reaffirm the investment in training and development in the Banking Industry is compensated. In line with the assertion made by the literature and the evidences gathered in the process of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. It is an established fact that no serious minded organization like banks can be staffed by people with expertise and potentials in the various disciplines needed for its total functioning simply by recruitment and selection. It is the systematic training and development of personnel on continuous basis that can harness the totality of human resources in

Reference

Coffman L. (1990) successful training programme evaluation, *Training and development journal* 34 Vol. 10

record of prospective employers in this vital area. Career progression and development is an increasingly attractive or even basic requirement for many such employees. In today's banking business climate where all industries are experiencing staff and skills shortages, companies are faced with stiff internal and external competition for quality employees. Each employer who invests seriously in the area of Training and Development will reap the benefits of an enriched working environment with higher levels of staff retention as well as increased productivity and performance.

the organization. It is therefore vital that managers as well as all employees receive the training. Nothing kills new learning as fast as the failure of the boss to understand and support it. Newly promoted and newly hired members of a group should also receive any training that is provided to the old staff. It is also advisable for senior executive to take related training.

2. Banks should ensure that any training and development which takes place is based on proper analysis of its contribution to the effectiveness and efficiency of banking industry. As far as training and development is concerned, is what happens after training. Ultimately training and development must be judged by its impact on the banking industry.

Ronald J. B (1999) A plea for a systematic evaluation of training, *Training and development journal*, 23 vol. 5 pp, 37-42

Mamoria (1996) personnel management (Rev. Ed.) Himalaya publishing House.

- Hesseling (1997). Evaluation of Management Training in some European countries, New York, Grijne and Statton.
- Hamlin (1994). Evaluation and Control of Training, McGraw Hill
- Scott, Clothier, and Spriegal, (1996). Personnel management. New Delhi, Tata McGraw-hill publishing house ltd, pg. 561.
- Banjoko, A. (1996). Human Resource Management: An Expository Approach. Saban Publishers Lagos. P. 71.
- Armstrong M. (1999) A handbook of Human Resource Management Practice, 7th Edition, London; Kogan
- Decenzo and Robbins (1996). Human Resource Management, 5th ed. Pp.237- 252, New York: John Wiley Sons Inc.
- Aswathapa K, (2008) Human Resource Management, Text and Cases, Fifth Edition, Tata McGraw- Hill Publishing Company Limited- 7 West Patel Nagar, New Delhi.
- Cascio F Wayne, (1998) Managing Human Resources, Productivity, Quality of Work Life, Profits, Fifth Edition, McGraw Hill
- Pattanayak Biswajeet,(2005) Human Resource Mnagement Third Edition, Prentice Hall of India, New Delhi-
- Pareek Udai, and Rao T V, (2006) Designing and Managing Human Resource Systems, Third Edition, Vijay Primlani for Oxford and IBH Publishing Company Private Limited-113-B- Shahapur, Jat-New Delhi
- Reddy and Rathan B (2007) Evaluating Training. Training and Development Journal, Vol.33, No.5, pp.14-22.
- Blake, R. R. (2006). Applied group dynamics training laboratories, *Journal of the American Society of Training Directors*, 14(1), 21-27.